

LUCÍA SOTO ÁLVAREZ

I, the undersigned Paula Muñoz, on behalf of Colegio Séneca S. Coop. And., sited in Córdoba (SPAIN), certify that:
Representing "Colegio Séneca S. Coop. And." from Spain,
attended the First in-person Mobility, under the project:
KA210 SteM rAising EnviRonmenTal Scientists

Córdoba, 6th to 9th May 2025

A handwritten signature in blue ink next to a circular official stamp. The stamp contains the text: "COLEGIO CONCERTADO SENECA S.C.A. F.º 14 - CORDOBA".

SIGNATURE

*KA210
SteM rAising
EnviRonmenTal
Scientists*

FRANCISCO J. MULET FERRER

I, the undersigned Paula Muñoz, on behalf of Colegio Séneca S. Coop. And., sited in Córdoba (SPAIN), certify that:
Representing "Colegio Séneca S. Coop. And." from Spain,
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KA210 SteM rAising EnviRonmenTal Scientists

Córdoba, 6th to 9th May 2025

A handwritten signature in blue ink next to a circular official stamp of Colegio Séneca S. Coop. And. The stamp contains the text: "COLEGIO CONCERTADO SENECA S.C.A. C/ G. I. 1. 14. CORDOBA".

SIGNATURE

KA210

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EnviRonmenTal
Scientists***

FRANCISCO JAVIER GONZÁLEZ MUÑOZ

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Scientists*

FISUN ÖZARTAN DEMİR

I, the undersigned Paula Muñoz, on behalf of Colegio Séneca S. Coop. And., sited in Córdoba (SPAIN), certify that: Representing "Dumlupınar ilkokulu Muğla" from Turkey, attended the First in-person Mobility, under the project:
KA210 SteM rAising EnviRonmenTal Scientists

Córdoba, 6th to 9th May 2025

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Scientists***

SEMA TOPLU

I, the undersigned Paula Muñoz, on behalf of Colegio Séneca S. Coop. And., sited in Córdoba (SPAIN), certify that:
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CENNET KARA GÜDEN

I, the undersigned Paula Muñoz, on behalf of Colegio Séneca S. Coop. And., sited in Córdoba (SPAIN), certify that: Representing "Dumlupınar ilkokulu Muğla" from Turkey, attended the First in-person Mobility, under the project: *KA210 SteM rAising EnviRonmenTal Scientists*

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M. OKAN ÇINAR

I, the undersigned Paula Muñoz, on behalf of Colegio Séneca S. Coop. And., sited in Córdoba (SPAIN), certify that:
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SIGNATURE

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EnviRonmenTal
Scientists*

ŞEHİRIBAN TAŞDELEN

I, the undersigned Paula Muñoz, on behalf of Colegio Séneca S. Coop. And., sited in Córdoba (SPAIN), certify that: Representing "Şehit Tuna Güzey İlköğretim okulu Eskişehir" from Turkey, attended the First in-person Mobility, under the project: *KA210 SteM rAising EnviRonmenTal Scientists*

Córdoba, 6th to 9th May 2025

SIGNATURE

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ADEM OĞUŞ

I, the undersigned Paula Muñoz, on behalf of Colegio Séneca S. Coop. And., sited in Córdoba (SPAIN), certify that: Representing "Şehit Tuna Güzey İlköğretim okulu Eskişehir" from Turkey, attended the First in-person Mobility, under the project: *KA210 SteM rAising EnviRonmenTal Scientists*

Córdoba, 6th to 9th May 2025

A handwritten signature in blue ink next to a circular official stamp. The stamp contains the text: "COLEGIO CONCERTADO SENECA S.C.A. E. G. I. 1.14 - CORDOBA".

SIGNATURE

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EnviRonmenTal
Scientists*

SIMGE BAYCAN ÇAKIR

I, the undersigned Paula Muñoz, on behalf of Colegio Séneca S. Coop. And., sited in Córdoba (SPAIN), certify that: Representing "Şehit Tuna Güzey İlköğretim okulu Eskişehir" from Turkey, attended the First in-person Mobility, under the project: *KA210 SteM rAising EnviRonmenTal Scientists*

Córdoba, 6th to 9th May 2025

A handwritten signature in blue ink and a circular green stamp. The stamp contains the text: "COLEGIO CONCERTADO SENECA S.C.A. Calle G. I. 1-14 - Córdoba".

SIGNATURE

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EnviRonmenTal
Scientists*

SONER ALBAYRAK

I, the undersigned Paula Muñoz, on behalf of Colegio Séneca S. Coop. And., sited in Córdoba (SPAIN), certify that: Representing "Şehit Tuna Güzey İlköğretim okulu Eskişehir" from Turkey, attended the First in-person Mobility, under the project: *KA210 SteM rAising EnviRonmenTal Scientists*

Córdoba, 6th to 9th May 2025

A handwritten signature in blue ink next to a circular official stamp. The stamp contains the text: "COLEGIO CONCERTADO SENECA S.C.A. E-11011 Córdoba".

SIGNATURE

*KA210
SteM rAising
EnviRonmenTal
Scientists*

KATARZYNA ŁASTAWIECKA

I, the undersigned Paula Muñoz, on behalf of Colegio Séneca S. Coop. And., sited in Córdoba (SPAIN), certify that:
Representing "Szkoły Podstawowej z Oddziałami Dwujęzycznymi nr 20 im. Jana Gutenberga Fundacji Szkolnej w Warszawie" from Poland, attended the First in-person Mobility, under the project: *KA210 SteM rAising EnviRonmenTal Scientists*

Córdoba, 6th to 9th May 2025

A handwritten signature in blue ink next to a circular official stamp. The stamp contains the text: "COLEGIO CONCERTADO SENECA S.C.A. FUNDACIÓN ESCOLAR 1974 - CORDOBA".

SIGNATURE

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SteM rAising
EnviRonmenTal
Scientists*

DOROTA ANDRYSKOWSKA-STOPPA

I, the undersigned Paula Muñoz, on behalf of Colegio Séneca S. Coop. And., sited in Córdoba (SPAIN), certify that:
Representing "Szkoły Podstawowej z Oddziałami Dwujęzycznymi nr 20 im. Jana Gutenberga Fundacji Szkolnej w Warszawie" from Poland, attended the First in-person Mobility, under the project: *KA210 SteM rAising EnviRonmenTal Scientists*

Córdoba, 6th to 9th May 2025

A handwritten signature in blue ink next to a circular green stamp. The stamp contains the text 'COLEGIO CONCERTADO SENECA S.C.A. FUNDACIÓN GUTENBERG 1-14 - CORDOBA'.

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Scientists*

ARKADIUSZ ZAWADA

I, the undersigned Paula Muñoz, on behalf of Colegio Séneca S. Coop. And., sited in Córdoba (SPAIN), certify that:
Representing "Szkoły Podstawowej z Oddziałami Dwujęzycznymi nr 20 im. Jana Gutenberga Fundacji Szkolnej w Warszawie" from Poland, attended the First in-person Mobility, under the project: *KA210 SteM rAising EnviRonmenTal Scientists*

Córdoba, 6th to 9th May 2025

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ROMAN RADOMSKI

I, the undersigned Paula Muñoz, on behalf of Colegio Séneca S. Coop. And., sited in Córdoba (SPAIN), certify that:
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